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ABSTRACTS

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VGEF Protein docking and modeling studies to target the angiogenesis pathway in cancer with flavanone derivatives

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Abstract: Plants and citrus fruits, such as oranges and lemons, naturally contain a molecule called flavanone, which has been shown to have anticancer properties. It primarily inhibits the apoptosis, cell cycle and angiogenesis. Since the bioavailability of flavanone is poor till today they are not considered as a prime therapeutic targets. It has been observed that modification of flavanone derivatives at its B- ring position may improve the bioavailability we used compound libraries like Drugbank, PubChem, and Sellkchem Database for this modification. VEGF having a molecular weight of 45 kilo Dalton which is homodimeric glycoprotein. It is a signaling protein and having a key role in embryogenesis and Angiogenesis. In cancer oncogene expression VEGF is the prime mediator of angiogenesis, in which it is up regulated by. For development and growth of tumor cell, it requires blood vessels for nutrients and oxygen. And angiogenesis process is essential for that. All of these factors will indicate that VEGF are the prime targets in cancer chemotherapy. The protein known as VEGF Receptor was obtained from the Protein Data Bank (PDBID: 4AG8). Using FlexX docking, the binding site was identified. FlexX docking software was used to dock flavanone and its congeners against the 4AG8 receptor protein. The Desmond Package was used to perform Molecular Dynamics simulations of the best-fitting molecule in order to validate the docking results. The potentials for stable conformations of non-covalent interactions such as electrostatic interaction, hydrogen bonding, and Vander Walls were computed. Therefore, using docking and molecular dynamics investigations, we were able to identify several flavanone derivatives that may be used as pharmacological targets to modulate VEGF arrest, including flavanone 39, flavanone 38, and flavanone 23. These compounds may also prove to be promising candidates for future cancer treatments.

Keywords: cancer, VEGF, flavanones, Molecular Docking, molecular Dynamics

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